

Quinazolones. Part V. Synthesis of Some Quinazolinoquinazolones

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A new route to the synthesis of 6-substituted quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-diones has been described.

While making an investigation on triazatetracyclic compounds resulting from the fusion of two quinazoline rings having one bridge head nitrogen atom, Butler and Partridge¹ prepared 6-methylquinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-dione (V) by methylating quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-dione (IV) with methyl sulphate and alkali. However, the compound so obtained was found to be different from that obtained directly by the action of methyl anthranilate on the waxy methyl derivative of 3,4-dihydro-2-mercapto-3-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V) although the ultraviolet absorption spectra of the two compounds were very similar. In order to remove the ambiguity, several syntheses were projected but became unsuccessful because of the inaccessibility of the starting materials. This prompted the author to evolve an easy, convenient and unambiguous new route to the synthesis of 6 substituted quinazolino(3,2-a)-quinazoline-5,12(6H)-diones which is the subject matter of this communication.

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| I : R = CH ₃ | V : R = H |
| II : R = Ph | VI : R = CH ₃ |
| III : R = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂ | VII : R = Ph |
| IV : R = H | VIII : R = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂ |

The reaction of 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-4H,1,3-thiazine with anthranilic acid to form 1,3-thiazino(2,3-b)-quinazolin-10-one² envisaged that the acid itself may condense with 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-thioquinazolin-4-one (IV) to form quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline diones (V). As the condensation at the alternative ortho position to form quinazolino(2,3-b)-quinazoline-dione is also not ruled out, it was considered necessary to block the nitrogen atom

1. K. Butler and M. W. Partridge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1512.
2. N. K. Ralhan, K. K. Aorula and H. S. Sachdev, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4061.

at position 3 so that quinazolino(2,3-a)quinazoline-dione may be the exclusive condensation product. Accordingly, 3 substituted 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-thioquinazolin-4-ones (I), (II) and (III) were considered as the suitable starting materials which on condensation with anthranilic acid would lead to the formation of 6 substituted quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-diones (VI), (VII) and (VIII) respectively. The synthetic sequence outlined has been realised and the author has been able to prepare three 6-substituted quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-diones (VI), (VII) and (VIII) as described below.

3-Methyl-2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one(I)¹, 3-phenyl-2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (II)³ and 3-allyl-2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (III)⁴ when mixed with equimolar proportion of anthranilic acid and the molten mixture heated for 5 hrs, till hydrogen sulphide no longer evolves, gave the corresponding quinazolinoquinazoline derivatives VI, VII and VIII in almost quantitative yield. A comparison of the infra-red and ultra-violet absorption spectra of the quinazolinoquinazolones so synthesised are almost similar and variation of substituents at position 6 do not in any way affect them. However, an additional IR absorption band at 709 cm⁻¹ is observed in case of the phenyl substituted compound, the other bands remaining the same. This leads us to conclude that the difference in the compounds synthesised by Butler and Partridge¹ was probably due to its isomerisation in alkali to quinazolino(2,3-b)quinazoline-5,7-dione before it was methylated.

As an extension of this method, the preparation of various quinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-diones having substituents in either of the benzene rings and a detailed study of their spectral properties is in progress and will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. Light petroleum used has the b.p. 60–80°.

6-Methylquinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-dione (VI): 3-Methyl-2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one¹ (I; 1.92 g.; 0.01 mole) was thoroughly mixed with anthranilic acid (1.37 g.; 0.01 mole) and the molten mixture was heated for 5 hr. in an atmosphere of CO₂ till H₂S no longer evolves. The hot molten reaction mixture was cooled, neutralised with 10% aq. Na₂CO₃ and filtered. The residue on crystallisation from ethanol afforded VI as colourless needles (1.6 g.; 60%), m.p. 177–178° (lit. m.p. 175–176°) IR(KBr) 1695, 1639, 1603 and 1493 cm⁻¹ λ_{max} (EtOH) 235 (ε, 41200), 283 (ε, 18400), 320 (ε, 4710) and 335 mμ (ε, 4430). (Found: C, 69.2; H, 3.8; N, 15.0. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₁O₂N₃: C, 69.3; H, 4.0; N, 15.2%).

6-Phenylquinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-dione (VII): A mixture of 3-phenyl 2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (II)³ (2.54 g.; 0.01 mole) and anthranilic acid (1.37 g.; 0.01 mole) was melted and the molten mixture heated in an oil bath (275–300°) in an atmosphere of CO₂ for 5 hr. till H₂S no longer evolves. The hot molten reaction mixture was

3. J. E. McCarty, E. L. Haines and C. A. Vander Werf, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 964.

4. T. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 981.

cooled and the jelly like solid which appeared in the flask was neutralised with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 and filtered. The residue was washed with water and two crystallisations from ethanol afforded VII as colourless cubes (2 g.; 60%), m.p. 196–197°. IR(KBr) 1695, 1603, 1493, 1299 and 709 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 233 (ϵ , 48950), 283 (ϵ , 24600), 320 (ϵ , 5820) and 336 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 4650). (Found : C, 74.1; H, 3.6; N, 12.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$: C, 74.3; H, 3.8; N, 12.3%).

6-*Allylquinazolino(3,2-a)quinazoline-5,12(6H)-dione* (VIII) : A mixture of 3-allyl-2-thio-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (III)⁴ (2.18 g.; 0.01 mole) and anthranilic acid (1.37 g.; 0.01 mole) when heated in a oil bath above their m.p. for 5 hr. in an atmosphere of CO_2 and worked up as in the previous case afforded a white jelly like solid which on crystallisation from ethanol gave VIII as colourless needles (1.5 g.; 50%), m.p. 165–166°. IR(KBr) 1695, 1639, 1603 and 1493 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 243 (ϵ , 46430), 285 (ϵ , 21350), 320 (ϵ , 5610) and 335 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 4350). (Found : C, 70.9; H, 4.0; N, 13.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$: C, 71.2; H, 4.3; N, 13.8%).

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